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MixITiN

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A Manual For Isolation And Culture Of Mixoplankton To
Support Experimental Studies

Per Juel Hansen, Kevin J Flynn, Aditee Mitra, Albert Calbet, Enric Saiz,
Paraskevi Pitta, Maira Maselli, Nikola Medić, Filomena Romano,
Claudia Traboni

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Lead author contact

Per Juel Hansen
University of Copenhagen, Faculty of Science
Marine Biological Section
Strandpromenaden 5
3000 Helsingør
Denmark
Email: pjhansen@bio.ku.dk

Project Co-ordinator contact

Aditee Mitra
School of Earth and Environmental Sciences
Cardiff University
Cardiff CF10 3AT
Wales, U.K.
Email: MitraA2@cardiff.ac.uk

Author affiliations

Per Juel Hansen, Marine Biological Section, University of Copenhagen, DK-3000, Helsingør, Denmark.

Kevin J Flynn, Plymouth Marine Laboratory, Plymouth, PL1 3DH, United Kingdom

Aditee Mitra, School of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Cardiff University, Cardiff, CF10 3AT, United Kingdom.

Albert Calbet, Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC, Pg. Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37-49, 08003, Barcelona, Spain.

Enric Saiz, Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC, Pg. Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37-49, 08003, Barcelona, Spain.

Paraskevi Pitta, Institute of Oceanography, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, PO Box 2214, 71003 Heraklion, Greece.

Maira Maselli, Marine Biological Section, University of Copenhagen, DK-3000, Helsingør, Denmark.

Nikola Medić, Marine Biological Section, University of Copenhagen, DK-3000, Helsingør, Denmark.

Filomena Romano, Institute of Oceanography, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, PO Box 2214, 71003 Heraklion, Greece

Claudia Traboni, Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC, Pg. Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37-49, 08003, Barcelona, Spain.

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1 Executive Summary

A manual for the isolation and maintenance of mixoplankton is provided that offer guidelines to assist students and scientists initiating studies of mixoplankton.

The manual contains specific information on:

- Facilities required, including temperature regulated rooms or cabinets, instruments and consumables
- Growth media and aseptic precautions
- General methods and recommendation for isolation of cells from nature and subsequent establishment of cell cultures
- Specific recommendation for the isolation and culture of different mixoplankton functional groups

2 Glossary

Items in italics are described elsewhere in this glossary. Some terms included here are not strictly required within this manual but may help interpreting other published materials.

α^C : the rate of photosynthesis per unit of C-biomass per photon. α^C characterises the initial slope of a C-specific *PE curve* (e.g., $\text{gC gC}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$ vs *PFD*).

α^{Chl} : the rate of photosynthesis per unit of chlorophyll per photon. α^{Chl} characterises the initial slope of a Chl-specific *PE curve* (e.g., $\text{gC gChl}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$ vs *PFD*).

Acclimation: changes in organism physiology in response to environmental factors. Often confused with *adaptation*, acclimation is an intra-generational response, though the topic is confused by epigenetic responses where acclimation extends over a few generations and is especially important during transfer of cultures to new growth conditions.

Adaptation: changes in the physiology of an organism that have come about through natural selection. Adaptation is an inter-generational response to changes in environmental factors (Cf. *acclimation*).

Allelochemical: chemicals that have negative impacts on competitors, and hence positive for the community releasing them. Typically, they are of unknown chemical characteristics, which may be destroyed by heat (e.g. during media preparation involving pasteurisation or sterilization) and light (notably, UV).

Anabolism: biochemistry that is constructive, making new biomass, at the expense of energy consumption. (Cf. *catabolism*.) In reality there are simultaneous anabolic and catabolic processes occurring as cellular components are continuously built, maintained and turned over.

Axenic: containing a single species. Usually implying cultures that are free of bacteria, fungi and viruses (Cf. *unialgal*).

Batch culture: a culture scenario in which a single one-off supply of nutrient is added to a culture that is left to grow typically through different phases of the culture dynamics, to stationary phase. While the culture may be sampled continuously, the system never enters or approaches a *steady-state* condition except perhaps at stationary phase. Unlike *chemostat* or *turbidostat* cultures, in batch systems the growth rate may approach the maximum possible rate. (Cf. *continuous culture*; *stretched batch culture*.)

Bioreactor: a vessel in which microbes, such as plankton are grown. Bioreactors come in different volumes (mL to 100's of cubic metres) and different forms, from small glass flasks, to ponds dug in clay, to sophisticated arrangements of pipes and pumps made of exotic materials. See also *Photobioreactor*.

Catabolism: biochemistry that consumes biomass, usually to generate energy. Cf. *anabolism*. In reality there are simultaneous anabolic and catabolic processes occurring as cellular components are continuously built, maintained and turned over.

Chelating agent: a chemical that holds on to other chemicals. Usually for microplankton culturing an organic compound that binds onto iron, Fe, keeping it in suspension and thus making it bioavailable. This may be artificial (as EDTA) or natural (as tannins or in “soil extract”).

Chemostat: a *continuous culture* system of constant volume into which fresh medium is introduced and at a similar rate expended medium complete with cells is withdrawn. At *steady-state* the organisms grow at the same rate as the specific dilution rate of the culture system. If the dilution rate is close to the maximum growth rate there is a risk of *washout*. See also *Turbidostat* and *Discontinuous culture*.

Chl: chlorophyll and often specifically chlorophyll *a*, the core photopigment, which is usually augmented by various accessory pigments that collect energy across other parts of the *PAR* spectrum.

Chl:C: the ratio (usually as mass) of chlorophyll to C-biomass. This ratio varies between species (typically with a maximum of 0.06 gChl/gC) and also increases during growth at low light and decreases with nutrient-stress. See also *photoacclimation*.

Ciliate: Phylum Ciliophora. A group of protists characterized by the presence of hair-like organelles called cilia, which are identical in structure to eukaryotic flagella, but are in general shorter and present in much larger numbers, with a different undulating pattern than flagella. Cilia occur in all members of the group with a few exceptions, and are variously used in swimming, crawling, attachment, feeding, and sensation. They are common in marine, brackish and freshwaters. Size range: 10-4000 μm . Most species are heterotrophic, but some (as non-constitutive mixoplankton; *NCM*) form either symbiosis with ingested algae or sequester functional chloroplasts from ingested photosynthetic prey. Prey range: bacteria and other protists.

CM: constitutive *mixoplankton*; a protist that has an innate, constitutive, ability to conduct photosynthesis and that is also able to phagocytise. (Cf. *NCM*.)

Compensation point: (C_p) the *PFD* at which *gross photosynthesis* = concurrent respiration; i.e. *net photosynthesis* is zero.

Continuous culture: a culture system in which, logistics constraints aside, growth continues (usually at steady-state) potentially forever. Cf. *batch culture*.

Cryptophytes: Phylum Cryptophyta. They have also been termed cryptomonads. Most species of this group of protists have chloroplasts, but some species without chloroplasts are known. They contain besides Chl *a* also the accessory pigments phycocyanin, allophycocyanin and/or phycoerythrin. They are common in marine, brackish and freshwater habitats. Size range (length): 6-50 μm . Cells are often flattened in shape, with an anterior groove or pocket. At the edge of the pocket, there are typically two slightly unequal flagella. The groove contains extrusomes, called ejectosomes. Suspected constitutive mixoplankton (*CM*). Prey: bacteria.

Dark reaction: the plateau value of the *PE curve*, limited primarily by the activity of *RuBisCO*.

Diatom: Phylum Bacillariophyta. Photosynthetic protists that (except for very few species) are characterised by a silica cell wall. Non-motile (except pennate diatoms may move slowly when in contact with a hard surface), robust, fast growing, and characteristic

of early spring bloom plankton growths in turbulent water. Sizes from 5 - 500µm as pennate (canoe-shaped) or centric (cylindrical) forms. Invariably mixotrophic by virtue of osmotrophy (many grow well in complete darkness on sugars and amino acids), but they are not mixoplankton as they cannot eat.

DIC: dissolved inorganic carbon, comprising CO₂ (the substrate for *RuBisCO*, for photosynthesis), bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) and carbonate (CO₃⁻).

DIN: dissolved inorganic nitrogen, comprising ammonia (NH₃), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻) and nitrite (NO₂⁻). NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻ are the usual main forms of DIN; NH₄⁺ is the “preferred” N-source in algal physiology but it is toxic at high residual concentrations (such as in undiluted anaerobic digestate liquors). Protists isolated from natural (low nutrient) waters may be highly sensitive to even moderate concentrations of ammonium (e.g., >50µM), even though ammonium is suspected to be the major DIN-source in nature.

Dinoflagellates: Phylum Dinoflagellata. Group of protists with approximately half of the known species lacking chloroplasts, and the other half capable of phototrophy by virtue of either being a *CM* or *SNCM*. They can be found in marine, brackish, and freshwaters. They can form blooms, often considered as harmful. Size range: 6-2000 µm. About half of the species (thecate species) carry cellulosic plates in vesicles (alveoli) under the cell membrane. Some species produce phycotoxins, which can accumulate in the food web or cause fish kills. Some species are parasites. Prey: other protists and in some cases metazoans. Their feeding mechanisms allow them to feed on relatively large prey, even prey that exceed their own size.

DIP: dissolve inorganic phosphorous, PO₄³⁻.

Discontinuous culture: like a *chemostat* culture (where dilution is continuous), but with a recurring discrete (e.g., once a day) replacement of a portion of the culture with fresh medium. Discontinuous removal has the advantage that a larger (and thus more useful volume of suspension) is removed for processing. A period of maximum growth rate is not seen. If the gap between sampling is sufficient, and the proportion of culture replaced also significant, then the discontinuous culture approaches a *stretched-batch culture* system.

DOC: dissolved organic carbon.

Down-shock: response cellular physiology to application of stress (e.g., by nutrient exhaustion). Down-shock results in the de-repression of physiological processes that are repressed during *up-shock*.

Ectosymbiont: Any organism that lives outside the body or cells of another organism most often, though not always, in a mutualistic relationship.

Endosymbiont: Any organism that lives within the body or cells of another organism most often, though not always, in a mutualistic relationship.

ESD: Equivalent Spherical Diameter – a transformed organism or particle volume to a spherical form thus standardising comparison between particles. Very few organisms are actually spherical and care should be taken in comparing, for example, organism ESD with pore sizes in filter-fractionations.

eSNCM: endosymbiotic specialist non-constitutive *mixoplankton*; these mixoplankton harbour selected species of intact endosymbiotic microalgae, which continue to perform photosynthesis, while growing inside the host protist. (Cf. *CM*, *GNCM*, *SNCM*.)

Exponential growth: a rate of growth when all organism-specific increases are constant. Best visualised as the linear (*steady-state*) portion of a plot of natural log (Ln) of cell numbers &/or biomass against time. The exponential growth rate does not necessarily equate to the maximum growth rate (though it is often confused with that).

GNCM: generalist non-constitutive *mixoplankton*; a protist that lacks an innate, constitutive, ability to perform photosynthesis and acquires its phototrophic potential from various other organisms. (Cf. *CM*, *GNCM*, *SNCM*.)

Gross photosynthesis: photosynthesis disregarding concurrent respiration that consumes part of the products of C-fixation. Gross photosynthesis is zero when PFD=0 (i.e., in darkness). (Cf. *net photosynthesis*.)

Haptophyte: a clade of organisms within the phylum Heterokontophyta. Most species have chloroplasts. The cells typically have two slightly unequal flagella, both of which are smooth, together with a unique organelle called a haptonema, which is superficially similar to a flagellum but differs in the arrangement of microtubules and in its use. The mitochondria in this group have tubular cristae (taxonomic aid). Many are suspected mixoplankton, feeding on prey ranging from bacteria to ca. 1/3rd their own size.

Heterotrophy: nutrition and growth supported by organic sources of carbon (Cf. *mixotrophy*, *osmotrophy*, *phagotrophy*, *phototrophy*).

in vitro: in test-tube, typically referring to quantification of materials extracted from organisms, which are invariably killed during the process. (Cf. *in vivo*.)

in vivo: in life, usually made in reference to measurements of processes or quantities within intact living organisms which are not usually killed in the process. (Cf. *in vitro*.)

Inoculum: cells introduced into a new culture system to initiate growth.

Light reaction: the strictly light-dependent phase of photosynthesis. In a plot of photosynthesis against light (the *PE curve*), this is the initial linear slope before the curve levels off to be limited by the *dark reaction*. The light reaction rate is limited, in addition to the *PFD*, by the photopigment complement that captures photons, the value of α^{Chl} , and at the cellular level by *Chl:C*.

Lugols' iodine: a common relatively-safe fixative used to immobilise and stain microbes prior to microscopy. It comes in many varieties, but the standard recipe contains Crystalline iod (I_2) and Potassium Iodine (KI). To make it mix 10 g KI and 5 g I_2 with 100 ml Milli-Q water. In an acidified version 10 ml of glacial acetic acid is added per 100 ml Lugol's solution. The solution should be stored in brown glass bottles. To fix a plankton sample add Lugol's 1 ml Lugol's per 100 ml water sample (=1% final concentration).

Macronutrient: nutrients that comprise the bulk of the biomass upon their assimilation and thus need to be added at high concentrations to the growth medium. For microalgae,

these are C (usually as *DIC* supplied as bicarbonate and via aeration, but possibly also by *DOC*), N (as *DIN*), and P (as *DIP*). For *diatoms*, Si is also a macronutrient. (Cf. *micronutrient*.)

Microloader tips: long, fine and flexible pipette tips.

Micronutrient: nutrients that comprise a minor component of the biomass upon their assimilation, and are thus usually added to culture media at only low concentrations. These include Fe and other metal cofactors, and vitamins and other organic cofactors. Micronutrients are just as essential as are macronutrients. (Cf. *macronutrients*. See also *soil extract* and *chelating agent*.)

Microplankton: Strictly plankton in the size range: 20-200 μm , but often used as a general term for microscopic plankton. (Cf. *nanoplankton*)

Mixoplankton: Planktonic protists that combine *phototrophy* and *phagotrophy*.

Mixotrophy: combining *phototrophy* and *heterotrophy*. (Cf. *heterotrophy*, *osmotrophy*, *phagotrophy*, *phototrophy*.)

Multidish: A (often disposable) tissue culture plate, often made out of polycarbonate.

Nanoplankton: Plankton in the size range: 2-20 μm . (Cf. *microplankton*)

NCM: non-constitutive *mixoplankton*; a planktonic protist that lacks an innate, constitutive, ability to conduct photosynthesis and thus acquires its phototrophic potential from (an)other organism(s). (Cf. *CM*, *GNCM*, *SNCM*.)

Net photosynthesis: photosynthesis including concurrent respiration that consumes some part of the products of C-fixation. Net photosynthesis is zero when *PPFD* is at the *compensation point*. (Cf. *gross photosynthesis*.)

Nutrient deplete: having less nutrient within the cell than is required to enable optimal (maximum) growth under current conditions, but growth can still continue. (Cf. *nutrient limited*, *nutrient stress*, *nutrient sufficient*.)

Nutrient limited: having so little of the nutrient in question that growth halts.

Nutrient replete: having more nutrient within the cell than is required for optimal (maximum) growth under current conditions. Thus surplus P may be accumulated as polyphosphate, and cells grown on ammonium-N have a higher *nutrient-status* (higher N:C) than do cells grown on nitrate-N. Nutrient replete cells will have repressed biochemical routes to using alternative nutrients that are de-repressed during the development of *nutrient stress*.

Nutrient-status: a statement of physiological status, of *nutrient stress*, with reference to a particular nutrient. Maybe referenced as a quotient, so 0 indicates a very poor status (*nutrient limited*) and 1 is *nutrient sufficient*. Nutrient status, and stress, is invariably associated with *up-shock* and *down-shock* events controlling different resource acquisition routes (e.g., switching between nutrient sources).

Nutrient stress: a condition between *nutrient sufficient* and *nutrient limited* during which various physiological processes are up- or down-regulated allowing the

(de)repression of alternative biochemical pathways. (Cf. *nutrient-status*. See also *down-shock* and *up-shock*.)

Nutrient sufficient: having sufficient nutrient within the cell to support optimal (maximum) growth under current conditions. (Cf. *nutrient replete*.)

Osmotrophy: a form of *heterotrophy* in which nutrition and growth is supported by the use of dissolved organic sources of carbon. (Cf. *heterotrophy*, *mixotrophy*, *phagotrophy*, *phototrophy*.)

PAR: photosynthetically active radiation; the portion of the light spectrum that is exploited by photosynthetic organisms. Coincidentally, this is the same as the visible spectrum for humans (light of wavelengths 400-700 nm).

PE curve: the relationship between light (E) and net of gross photosynthesis (P), characterised by an initial upward slope (*light reaction*) and a plateau value (set by the maximum *dark reaction* rate).

Phagotrophy: a form of *heterotrophy* in which nutrition and growth is supported by the consumption of organic particles; usually such particles are other organisms and the phagotrophy is de facto a form of predation. (Cf. *heterotrophy*, *mixotrophy*, *osmotrophy*, *phototrophy*.)

Photoacclimation: *acclimation* of microalgae to the supply and demand of photosynthesis balanced against light and nutrient (usually *DIN* or *DIP*) supply. Characterised by changes in *Chl:C* and often also changes in other photo-pigments, and also in the level of *RuBisCO*.

Phototrophy: nutrition and growth supported by assimilation of inorganic sources of carbon (de facto, CO₂) through photosynthesis. (Cf. *heterotrophy*, *mixotrophy*, *osmotrophy*, *phagotrophy*.)

PFD: photo flux density (photons m⁻² s⁻¹); the number of photons hitting a stated area per unit of time. A light meter for biological use may report this as *PAR PFD*, as just that part of the light energy spectrum of use for photosynthesis (wavelengths 400-700 nm). Note that photons of different wavelengths contain different amounts of energy; a photon at 400 nm contains approaching twice (i.e., 700/400) of the energy of a photon at 700 nm.

Plankton wheel: a device that rotates at an adjustable speed (using at most a few rpm) upon which plankton bottles are strapped. The bottles (usually with little, or no, head space) rotate so keeping plankton in suspension.

pSNCM: plastidic specialist non-constitutive mixoplankton; these acquire and exploit only the plastids originating from another organism. (Cf. *CM*, *GNCM*, *SNCM*.)

Q₁₀: the proportion by which biological process rates (e.g., growth rate) increases when temperature is increased by 10°C. Traditionally a value of Q₁₀ = 2-3 is assumed. The value is only useful within a narrow temperature window above which thermal detrimental effects, including death, occurs rapidly.

rSNCM: reduced specialist non-constitutive mixoplankton; protists that acquire and exploit prey organelles such as prey nuclei, prey mitochondria, and prey cytoplasm with

ribosomes along with the prey chloroplasts. (Cf. *CM*, *GNCM*, *SNCM*.) They differ from eSNCMs that exploit intact prey cells.

RuBisCO: ribulose biphosphate carboxylase; the enzyme responsible for fixing CO₂ (a component of *DIC*, perhaps allied with *carbonic anhydrase*, *CA*). On account of it having a rather low efficiency (low k_{cat}) and of the importance of primary production to life on Earth, RuBisCO is considered to be the most important single enzyme on the planet. At high O₂ concentrations (O₂ being a by-product of the *light reaction* of photosynthesis, q.v.), CO₂-fixation by RuBisCO is inhibited.

SNCM: specialist non-constitutive mixoplankton; these acquire and exploit plastids and in some cases also other cell organelles and cytoplasm originating from another organism. (Cf. *CM*, *GNCM*.)

Soil extract: a source of natural chelating agents and micro-nutrients, prepared by boiling 1 kg of soil from a low-nutrient location in 1 L of pure water, added to growth media at a dose of 1 mL L⁻¹ prior to sterilisation.

Specific growth rate: growth rate made in reference to a specific component. A value of 0.693 d⁻¹ describes a doubling per day; 0.693 = Ln(2). It should be noted that depending on the reference component, the value of the specific growth rate is not the same when measured by different parameters. Thus, cell-specific (cell cell⁻¹ d⁻¹) often differs from C-specific (C C⁻¹ d⁻¹), and differs from N-specific (N N⁻¹ d⁻¹), etc. Only in a culture growing at true steady-state in a heterogeneous culture (organisms at all different stages of their cell cycle) will all specific growth rates be the same as averaged across the whole population. Unfortunately, because the units of the specific component cancel out, usually only the time unit is reported (e.g., d⁻¹); full units should therefore always be given.

Steady-state: a condition where all processes are progressing in unison, such that the *specific growth rate* as determined through reference to any/all components will be equal. The biochemistry of individual cells can be in steady-state while the population abundance is changing (not in steady-state). Steady-state is best achieved through growth in a *chemostat* or *turbidostat*. In steady-state, the growth rate is *exponential*. Growth in steady-state usually implies growth limited by a factor; non-decaying dead cells are also in steady-state. See also *specific growth rate*.

Stretched batch culture: a batch culture system into which fresh medium is added to balance the removal of volumes for sampling. This is a form of *discontinuous culture* in which the sample taken is so large and/or so infrequent, that the culture expresses a period of *batch culture* dynamics, including the potential for growth at the maximum possible rate.

Tangential-flow filtration: a filtration methodology in which the suspension being filtered is passed over the face of the filter (at a tangent) to continuously removing particles from the face of the filter that would otherwise block the filter pores. This method is particularly useful for ultra-filtration of large volumes of media.

Turbidostat: a continuous culture system that, in contrast to the operation of the *chemostat*, has a control of entry of fresh medium and simultaneous removal of spent medium and culture linked to the optical density of the culture suspension. Unlike the

chemostat, dilution rates in a turbidostat can run close to the maximum growth rate without risk of *washout*.

Unialgal: single algal species. Often used to describe a culture that contains bacteria, but only one algal species. Cf *axenic*.

Up-shock: recovery of cellular physiology from stress (e.g., by supply of nutrients to a nutrient-starved culture). Up-shock results in the repression of physiological processes that were de-repressed during *down-shock*.

Validation: a process through which the output from a *simulation model* is compared with the real world to convince the user that the *simulation* is fit for purpose.

Washout: an event when the dilution rate of a culture system (*bioreactor*) exceeds the growth rate of the organism, so washing out the culture. Washout is common in a *chemostat* at high dilution rates but will not occur in a *turbidostat*.

3 Introduction

Throughout this manual we use the term *mixoplankton* (Flynn et al. 2019) in reference to protists that are mixotrophic by virtue of combining phototrophy and phagotrophy. The manual contains methods on how to isolate, grow and prepare mixoplankton for experiments. **Fig. 1** provides a simple classification of the different protist plankton functional types.

Fig.1. Classification key for planktonic protists. Updated from Mitra et al. (2016).

To gain information on the ecophysiology of mixotrophic protists, ready access to robust laboratory cultures of recent isolates is critical. In principle, many constitutive mixoplankton (CMs) can be cultured using standard “microalgae” (phytoplankton) cultivation techniques (e.g., Laring 1991, Andersen 2005); however, some have special requirements, and they will not grow in such growth media. Indeed, it has long been noted that culture collections are rather lacking in protist plankton typical of mature ecosystems, which we now appreciate as being the types of environments in which mixoplankton thrive. Understanding the reasons for these special culture requirements are likely the key for helping to understand their physiology and their role in pelagic food webs.

The non-constitutive mixoplankton (NCMs) sequester photosystems from their prey and are generally not available from protistan culture collections. This reflects the high level of frequent attention that such cultures require, with a requirement for the simultaneous culturing of their prey. Thus, NCMs typically have to be isolated from environmental samples, and cultures need to be established as and when they are required. Bringing NCM's into culture has often proven to be difficult and this has significantly hindered studies of their physiology and explains why so little information is available on them.

An additional challenge is that while some mixoplankton are omnivorous, others have a very restricted prey range, in term of types and sizes, and perhaps also of nutritional status. Some mixoplankton may require mixed diets for optimal growth, further complicating their routine culturing. Although such matters are well appreciated by practitioners, nevertheless, information on this subject is still quite sparse in the literature.

The following sections present a guide to facilities and consumables required to isolate, establish and maintain cultures of different mixoplankton functional types.

4 Facilities, instruments and consumables

4.1 Facilities

4.1.1 Homogeneity of growth conditions

Control of temperature (4.1.2) and light (4.1.3) should be considered together because they are closely associated, not least because non-LED lighting generates significant heat which must be removed. Maintaining homogeneity for individual cells with respect to temperature and light within the culture are factors that need consideration at the same time. Many of these organisms will swim to or away from light sources, and thence to or away from the heat those lights generate; this adversely affects attempts to standardise growth conditions.

Many mixoplankton are also adversely affected by stirring or aeration, and many researchers just gently swirl culture flasks once a day or so (and certainly before sampling in experiments). Swirling itself must be done with care else cells aggregate to the centre or conversely to the walls of the flask. One way to thoroughly but gently mix the suspension is to swirl the flask gently and then to hold it still at an angle to allow the final water motion to “fold-in” the cell suspension.

4.1.2 Temperature

Protists are generally sensitive to changes in temperature, so access to facilities with temperature regulation is required during cell isolation and culture work. This is best achieved with a “walk-in” climate room (often referred to as constant temperature or CT rooms), see **Fig. 2**.

If such CT rooms are not available, a temperature cabinet can be used for cultures, but for temperature sensitive species this is not the best option (**Fig. 2**). Certainly, that is so for experimentation, as exposure to external air when sampling may affect the water temperature; this is particularly a problem with small culture containers of < 50 mL volume.

Fig. 2. Left: Climate room. Middle and right: an example of a culture cabinet that can be used for algal cultures.

Temperatures for reproducible results in experiments should not deviate more than $\pm 0.5-1$ °C, and some form of ventilation is required to keep temperatures stable, especially at high irradiances, because light sources and other equipment (and also including humans) generate heat. If the cultures are brought outside from the climate rooms or cabinets for a short time period it is important to maintain temperature stable using water baths (**Fig. 3**).

Fig. 3. In cases where small volume containers are brought outside for sampling it is advisable to keep them in water baths to avoid deviations of the temperatures at which they are grown.

4.1.3 Lighting

Growth rooms and cabinets should be equipped with “daylight” type light sources. This can either be “cool white” fluorescent lamps or LED type light (colour: daylight). Whichever light source is used, it should give the entire photosynthetical active radiation (PAR) spectrum. If

UV light is desired (though this is not normally so) special light sources will need to be acquired and appropriate safety measures taken to protect staff. In such cases, Quartz bottles should be used as these allow for UV light penetration; borosilicate glass (e.g., Pyrex) or polycarbonate bottles do not allow UV light to pass through.

Lighting panels can either be mounted at the side of the wall or above/below the culture flasks (**Fig. 4**). The advantage of using light coming from below is that light is not shadowed by any stoppers. Light can be measured in air as well as directly in the water with an appropriate light meter, ideally equipped using a 4π (spherical) sensor. Waterproof light sensor probes with a small diameter are best since they can go directly into even small containers, allowing for measurements of the photon flux density directly in the water.

Fig. 4. Mounting of light sources depending on the size of incubation bottles to insure the most uniform photon flux density. Left: light mounted from the side for large bottles; right: Light mounted from below for smaller flasks.

To mimic changes in light associated with the diurnal cycle, the lighting of the CT room or cabinet needs to be configured for a light:dark (L:D) cycle. L:D cycles of 14 hrs : 10 hrs and 16 hrs : 8 hrs are most often chosen, though for sampling twice a day, a 12:12 cycle is easier.

Light is typically reported as photon flux density (PFD) with units of $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; there is a lot of confusion in the literature on the topic of light units and transformation between units is non-trivial (see Thimijan & Heins, 1983). While full sunlight has a PFD of the order of $2000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, because plankton live in a mixed layer typically of many metres depth, and light is rapidly absorbed by both the plankton itself and any other coloured material in the water, light as received by plankton in the water column (as distinct from at the very surface) is more likely $<10\%$ of surface levels (e.g., $10\text{-}200 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). This is convenient because typical lighting systems have problems producing more than $200 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ at the surface of the culture vessels.

For maintenance of mixoplankton cultures, depending on the species, the required light level would be between 10 and $100 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Lower light levels may be used to slow

down the growth of mixoplankton, especially CMs and SNCMs in stock cultures, and thereby lengthening the period between sub-culturing and re-feeding with prey. As with the choice of temperature, the best values for a given species or strain will have to be determined by trial and error.

For most experimental purposes, irradiance of up to 200 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ will be sufficient; indeed, levels $> 200 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ may be difficult to achieve and/or inhibitory. Many mixoplankton species are stressed at high PFD, while local heating in a culture vessel (even if the room or cabinet reports a stable temperature) may become a problem at high irradiances and can be mitigated by either using a fan, using a Peltier cooling platform, or by submersion of the bottles in a water bath.

4.1.4 Aseptic Precautions

To maintain the mixoplankton stock cultures free of contamination by other non-intended protists, the cultures should be re-inoculated and fed by manipulations undertaken within the controlled environment of a laminated flow bench. Such a bench, or cabinet, provides a flow of **sterile air** flowing over the culture vessels towards the operative. A laminar air-flow cabinet must not be confused with a fume hood, which draws in (non-sterile) air from the laboratory.

Standard aseptic microbiological precautions should be exercised (e.g., use of a Bunsen burner in the laminar air-flow cabinet during culture work and experimentation), including for the removal and destruction of culture media and cultures after their usage.

Important: on no account must any culture be disposed down a standard drain. Local rules must be followed for disposal. These invariably involve killing the organisms by heat (usually autoclaving) or addition of chemicals (usually domestic bleach).

Once a culture is established, proper identification of the isolate is required. This involves access to appropriate instrumentation.

4.2 Instruments

4.2.1 Microscopes

Access to different types of microscopes is required.

Compound and **inverted microscopes** are required for checking the state of the cultures. These should ideally be equipped for camera usage for documentation of mixoplankton cultures by photographs and videos. Such microscopes are usually equipped with x10 eye pieces fitted with an eye piece graticule, calibrated against a stage micrometer; this enables the viewer to measure the dimensions of the cells.

For mixoplankton work, these microscopes should be equipped with a minimum of x10, x20 and x40 objectives. Although of value, x4 and x100 objectives are for specific purposes if you work with large protists ($>100 \mu\text{m}$) or bacteria, respectively (**Fig. 5**). Further, it is useful if the microscopes are equipped with phase contrast or Nomarski interference contrast (NIC) modules, and dark field at low magnifications.

Access to an **epifluorescence microscope** will be very useful for doing experimentation requiring the visualization of chloroplasts (which return red signal upon illumination with blue light), ingested prey and nuclei usually stained with UV excitable compounds which give blue return signal (**Fig. 5**). Nuclei stain and observation is also a valuable tool to inspect cultures for the presence of potential contaminant, such as heterotrophic flagellates and bacteria which are common when working in non-completely sterile environments. Fixation is required to permeabilize the cell membranes to stains. Transparent fixatives, such as glutaraldehyde and formaldehyde are usually preferred.

A **dissecting or stereo microscope** (magnification x4-60 times) is very useful for isolation of larger (>10 μm) cells, and for checking the state of the cultures. Such a dissecting microscope should be equipped with a light source that provides light coming from below, and also, if possible, with “dark field” illumination. New models are provided with LED lighting that avoids the warming of the sample.

Fig. 5. Mixoplankton specimens (*Strombidium Cf. conicum*) in (A) bright field light microscopy, 20x magnification (B) epifluorescence microscopy, blue light excitation, 20x magnification

4.2.2 Enumeration

Several techniques can be used to quantify the numeric abundance of cells. These include manual counts as well as machine counters. Manual counting can be undertaken by using, for example a Sedgewick Rafter counting chamber under a microscope and requires the use of fixatives (**Fig. 6**). Lugol’s solution is often employed as a fixative to prepare samples for manual counting, since it is relatively less toxic for the environment and the operator compared to other commonly used fixatives. Lugol’s solution, at the same time, stains polysaccharides in a brown dark colour. This characteristic could facilitate the counting of small cells, but prevents the observation of the cellular content required to assess the potential feeding activity. Different machine counters used for mixoplankton include particle counters such as those working on the Coulter principle, particle image analysers such as FlowCam, and flow cytometers (**Fig. 6**). Machine counters can be employed to enumerate live samples, although fixation with the aforementioned transparent fixatives is required to allow staining and enumeration of cellular compartments (such as lysosomes or food vacuoles) and bacterial cells.

All these counting techniques have different pros and cons, and the preferred method depends on the size and concentration of the mixoplankton cells in the cultures, and the presence of other cells (e.g., their prey) and particles. Notably, however, while particle counters are excellent at determining particle volumes, they cannot discriminate between inert particles and cells, or between different species of similar size. Flow cytometers are poor at determining cell size, this being inferred by other signals. While different sized beads can be used to get the approximate size of the organisms such beads do not typically

conform to the shape or surface structure of organisms and thus provide different reflective signals.

In addition to the above methodologies, photosynthetic pigments, like chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*), are widely used as a measure of cell concentration. However, this technique is not reliable as a sole technique for counting plankton cells or determining biomass (Kruskopf & Flynn 2006). In order to have reliable cell concentration data from chlorophyll *a* measurement, data will need to be verified using other quantification techniques, since cellular levels of Chl *a* are sensitive to irradiance and nutrient limitation by a factor of >5.

Fig. 6. Top left: Sedgewick-Rafter chambers are useful for manual counting of mixoplankton. Flow cytometers (top right) and Coulter counters (bottom figures) are examples of machine counters that are useful for the enumeration of live and fixed cells.

Video 1. How to fill a Sedgewick-Rafter chamber. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5907181>

4.2.3 pH meter

A **pH meter** is required when preparing media for culturing mixoplankton. Seawater pH is ~8. However, the pH in cultures will vary. Thus, pH will increase due to the uptake of inorganic carbon in a system of net phototrophy. In contrast, pH will decline in a system of net heterotrophy, which includes a system where bacterial growth exceeds that of phototrophic mixoplankton, for example.

Seawater pH will rise in cultures of surprisingly low abundance of photosynthetically active cells; this elevated pH will negatively impact the growth of the cultures (Hansen 2002, Hansen et al 2007). The amount of macro-nutrients that on conversion into biomass during photosynthesis result in such an increase in pH is only around 50-100 μM dissolved inorganic-N (DIN); in contrast, the classic f/2 growth medium of Guillard (1978) has 880 μM of DIN. To guard against unwittingly killing cultures through the usage of high DIN resulting in elevated pH, growth medium equating to f/20 (i.e., 88 μM DIN) should be used. If dense cultures are needed, bubbling with atmospheric air using glass tubes and pumps may be applied in some cases (see **Video 2**).

Video 2. Bubbling of 10L mixoplankton cultures. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5907194>

4.2.4 Other equipment

Other items required include the following:

- Salinometer (ideally electronic, though a refractometer may suffice); this is needed if using near-shore water as the base for growth media, and of course in conducting experiments on salinity.
- Top-pan balance for bulk chemical preparations and high precision balance for the preparation of nutrient and vitamin standards.
- Assorted pipettes, including high volume (5, 10, 20 mL) for sampling. These large pipettes are usually best used with tips that have been trimmed to enlarge the orifice diameter to ensure that sampling does not create shear that kills the cells during transfers.
- Domestic-grade fridge (growth media components) and freezers: -20°C for most samples for analysis and -80°C for ultra-low temperature storage (DNA etc).
- Access to autoclaves large enough to take culture vessels complete with any additional pipework for sampling etc. For small water volumes, a microwave will also work.
- Oven (muffle furnace) for preparing ashed glass-fibre filters for elemental analysis ($450-500^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5h).
- Acid bath – a traditional way to clean glassware is to soak it in chromic acid or HCl. Be sure to rinse the glassware thoroughly afterwards. Many prefer to avoid the use of detergents because a lot of rinsing is required afterwards, however if detergents are used, use a liquid form such as Decon 90 or Neutracon for pH neutral cleaning (essential for polycarbonate bottles which are destroyed by other means).
- Reverse osmosis (RO) water and/or HPLC grade water (used in preference to single or double distilled water, respectively).

4.3 Consumables

Basic consumables are needed to work with mixoplankton cultures. Mixoplankton can be grown in both polycarbonate and glass containers (but see section 4.2.2 about need for Quartz containers when using UV light). Care must be taken in the final washing of such containers, ideally using reverse-osmosis, heat sterilized or HPLC-grade water, to ensure that all residues of cleaning agents are rinsed off. Also, polycarbonate containers are destroyed by some cleaners; care instructions must be followed.

With disposable plastic containers, be aware that many manufactures coat the container inside with different “anti-stick” chemicals (to prevent mammalian cell-line adherence) that may be toxic to the protists. It is thus important to check if that might be a problem for your protist of interest, and to repeat such checks with new batches of containers. Some companies provide non-coated plastic ware. Otherwise coating can be removed by rinsing the container with clean culture media several times before inoculating the culture.

Isolation of mixoplankton (> 15 μm ESD) from natural seawater are often done in multi-dishes (96, 24 or 6 wells), while cultures are then maintained in tissue culture flasks (for instance 60, 250, 750 mL). Multi-dishes must be covered with parafilm, or similar, to prevent evaporation and hence changes in salinity. Cultures maintained in glass (Pyrex, Schott) bottles (50-10,000 mL) also need a lip or a cotton stopper to prevent evaporation.

Isolation of smaller mixoplankton cells (< 15 μm ESD) is usually done by adding a drop of water with the protist of interest to a microscopy slide. It is then micro-pipetted and added to a multi-dish or a small tissue culture flask (see 5.1.1). For stock cultures, it is helpful to grow these in small tissue bottles which can be checked under a dissecting microscope (Section 4.2.1).

4.4 Growth media

4.4.1 Seawater base

Most scientists use natural seawater as the basis for the growth media of microalgae (which includes mixoplankton), but defined (artificial) media can also be used in some instances (Andersen 2005).

Defined media is made by mixing reagent-grade (or higher grade) salts with water of at least reverse osmosis grade. There are also commercial salts available via the aquaculture and aquarium trades, such as “Instant Ocean” (<http://www.instantocean.com/>); these may have high DIC (bicarbonate) concentrations as the bicarbonate helps maintain the aquaria pH constant. All defined media contain contaminants which may be of importance (positively or negatively), but usually such media have a repeatable composition.

If natural seawater is selected as the basis of the growth media, care needs to be taken sourcing it. Often near-shore waters that are easiest to sample are also loaded with nutrients washed off the shore. The water is brought to the laboratory and typically stored at 4-6°C in the dark (dark containers) for weeks before use. This “ages” the water. Check the containers do not contain, or are composed of, materials that are toxic to the cultures. Storage is not required but may be advisable to ensure that most of the protists in the water are dead, and remineralization has taken place. On the contrary, and because remineralisation can result

in elevated nutrient levels, an alternative approach is to spike the water with a diatom (such as *Thalassiosira weissflogii*) and keep the container at low light at ~15°C; the diatoms consume the nutrients and then sink to the bottom of the vessel – careful syphoning of the water then provides a source of low-nutrient, low particulate seawater.

Next the seawater needs to be filtered to remove particulates. This step starts by careful syphoning of the water; it is unwise to shake the storage container, or to attempt to use the last litres as this will contain all those particles that had settled during storage. The water should then be filtered through a relatively wide-pore glass-fibre (GF) filter to remove particles above several µm ESD.

The water can then be sterilized by passing it through a 0.2 µm filter being sure to conduct a bubble-point test at the end of the process to check for filter integrity. Positive pressure should be used for all such filtration, else the water becomes degassed and the DIC equilibria (which controls pH) is disturbed. Preparation of large volumes of water for experimental work is readily and quickly achieved using large-surface area cartridge filters of 0.2 µm, but there is always a concern as to whether filtration is truly establishing sterility. This is because the smallest bacteria may pass through what is a nominal 0.2 µm mesh filter. For this reason, many prefer to use heat sterilized media for critical applications, such as maintaining bacteria-free cultures.

Seawater can be pasteurized or sterilized by heating to either 95°C for 90 minutes or 121°C for 20 minutes in an autoclave. Heating seawater >100°C may lead to precipitation of carbonates, phosphates and silicates, creating transparent crystal “flakes” that will be observed in the heat-treated medium. Such precipitates are undesirable and can be removed by letting the precipitates settle 2-3 days before use (though of course they then remove nutrients). However, as confirmed by microscopy and particle analysis, such media invariably still contain a lot of crystalline material of a similar size to the microplankton and which then confuse especially electronic counters (flow cytometers, Coulter counters). The water can be filtered after the heat treatment to remove this particulate matter but such post heat-treatment filtration is impractical with larger volumes of water and rather removes the purpose of using heat to guarantee sterility in the first instance.

Another drawback with heating seawater is that it loses inorganic carbon during heating due to the precipitation of CaCO₃; the water may lose ~30% of its inorganic carbon content if sterilized at 121°C. This loss decreases the pH buffer capacity of the seawater media, possibly leading to lower cell yields in the cultures. To compensate for this loss, inorganic carbon may be added (in form of NaHCO₃) to the final growth medium, but again this carries a real risk of breaking the sterility. Pragmatically then, stock cultures for which sterility is deemed essential, are usually held in media that has been autoclaved.

4.4.2 Nutrients

Nutrients are typically added after the bulk sea water has been sterilized (by filter or heat). These are usually added either as a heat-sterilized concentrate by pipette, or (more commonly) by syringe through a 0.2 µm filter. This route is followed because if added before the bulk water is treated, a lot of the nutrients are lost onto filters or into crystals. This is especially true of Fe (iron), phosphate and silicate.

Standard microalgal (“phytoplankton”) growth media additions can be used to grow mixoplankton. Popular algal growth media include f/2 and the L-media (Guillard 1975,

Guillard and Hargraves 1993). They are typically based on natural seawater but are very rich in macronutrients, micronutrients and vitamins. For reasons noted above (Section 3.2.2), for most purposes it is advisable to use a ten times dilution (thus f/20 or L/10 media), unless very dense cultures are explicitly required and additional inorganic C is added (as sodium bicarbonate). Alternatively, atmospheric air or a 5% (by volume) air/CO₂ gas may be applied.

To explain this latter point, consider that DIC is typically present in seawater at 2000 μM, and the cellular C:N in nutrient sufficient cells is of the order of 10. Given that DIC controls pH and also provides pH buffering, it is best to avoid consuming more than ~1000 μM DIC, which with a C:N of 10 would equate to a consumption of 100 μM DIN. Some species will continue growing, fixing CO₂, while the C:N continues to rise on exhaustion of the DIN. If the object of the culture is to grow cells into nutrient limitation unhindered by pH, then the added DIN should be in the region of only 50 μM.

It is thus not surprising that a problem with using full strength media (e.g., f/2 DIN = 880 μM) is that pH in water becomes very high as the cultures grow denser. This is particularly the case for those cultures that are primarily phototrophic. As the cultures grow in high nutrient waters, pH increases until the stationary growth phase is reached, often set by the pH tolerance of the species in question and not by nutrient availability (as is often assumed).

Bubbling can be applied in some cases (typically in the case of small to medium sized CMs), but in other cases this is not possible as many mixoplankton cultures (most dinoflagellates and ciliates, i.e., many NCMs and large CMs) are vulnerable to shear (see 4.1.1). Artificial buffers (Tris, HEPES) to control the medium pH should be avoided since the cultures then may become limited by inorganic carbon instead, and these buffers (added at many mM) are themselves potential sources of C and/or N (containing, even in HPLC-grade chemicals, various other organics at μM levels).

Inorganic nitrogen is usually added as nitrate (NO₃⁻) but it should be noted that some species are unable to exploit this form of DIN. Ammonium (NH₄⁺) has to be added to the growth medium for such cultures, and in nature (given that many mixoplankton grow in the low nitrate summer months) this may be their most important DIN source. However, it should be noted that NH₄⁺ can be toxic to the CMs if applied in concentrations > 50 μM, especially as NH₃ (which passes readily through cell membranes) becomes the increasingly dominant form as pH increases. This is an additional reason to routinely restrict DIN to around the 50 μM level. For bacteria-free cultures, organic N-sources (urea, dissolved free amino acids, purine etc.) can be used; these (excepting urea) also support a level of mixotrophy via osmotrophy.

Phosphorus (P) is usually supplied as phosphate, although glycerophosphate can be used in bacteria-free cultures. P addition is usually in the mole ratio 16:1 N:P. If there is a need to grow cultures into P-stressed conditions, the nutrient regime needs to have a very significant excess in N (in excess of 32:1, and ideally closer to 64:1 of N:P). As, from above, the DIN concentration should be in the region of 50-100 μM, this means that initial DIP needs to be in the order of only 1 μM. Often un-aged seawater contains that level of DIP; DIP in the source base seawater should thus be measured prior to making up growth media. Because stock cultures are often held at much high nutrient concentrations, it can also take some time for residual (excess) DIP to be consumed or diluted out. Ultimately, the cellular C:N:P is what matters, and not the N:P of the growth media.

Vitamins and other micronutrients are usually added in considerable excess (see Andersen 2005). Natural waters also contain a wide range of (often poorly characterised) organic matter which provides micronutrients for many species. Thus, tannins act as chelating agents for the essential micro-nutrient iron (Fe). The culture of some species on defined media may require the addition of soil-extracts to provide such organics (the alternative being to add artificial chelators such as EDTA).

5 Isolation techniques and initial culture of mixoplankton

5.1 General techniques and recommendations (with reference to previously published papers on the topic)

5.1.1 Cell isolation

Mixoplankton can generally be isolated using standard procedures for “microalgae” (see for instance Loring 1991 and Andersen 2005). Isolation of cells is usually done using a drawn out Pasteur glass pipette or a microloader (Eppendorf) pipette tip (see **Figs. 7, 8** and **Video 3**). The selected tip is mounted onto a silicon tube and a mouthpiece is attached to the other end of the tube (ideally with a suitable filter for protection of the scientist).

Fig. 7. The mouth pipette made from a silicon tube where either a drawn Pasteur pipette or a microloader pipette tip can be mounted in one end and a mouth-piece in the other end.

Video 3. Drawing a Pasteur pipette for isolation of single mixoplankton cells.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5907204>

Microloader tips are easier to use because they do not break like drawn out glass pipettes, but like the multidishes, they may be coated with anti-stick chemicals and will need to be rinsed in sterile blank seawater several times before use. Manufactures often also coat microscopy slides with different anti-stick compounds to enhance spreading of a drop of water etc. on the slide. To avoid contamination from such anti-stick compounds and also spreading of the water droplet, the slide should be washed in demineralized water; this will ensure that the water droplet will be confined to a small area, greatly enhancing the survival of the mixoplankton cell. Alternatively, glass slides can be flamed (with care!) using a Bunsen burner.

Fig. 8. Isolation of mixoplankton using a mouth pipette and multidishes.

Isolation of cells has to be quick as the microscope lamp will heat the slide and fairly quickly kill the protists. For larger mixoplankton ($> 15 \mu\text{m}$ ESD) it is advantageous to do the isolation using multi-dishes (e.g., 96, 24, 6 wells) instead of on microscopy slides. See also comments in Section 3.3.

It is important that the isolation of cells is done at temperatures similar to that at the sampling location, since many of the species are quite sensitive to quick changes in temperature. This is best done directly in a “walk in climate room” (see Section 4.1.1). In ultra-oligotrophic waters the concentration of larger mixoplankton is low. For this reason, addition of prey directly to the collected seawater NCMs 2-3 days prior to isolation will allow the mixoplankton to increase in cell density and make the isolation steps easier.

Isolated cells are added to containers, which can be multidishes (**Figs. 8 and 9**), small glass tubes, and tissue culture bottles, with sterile filtered seawater from the sampling. Prey are then added to the containers with the isolated cells. The types and amount of prey to add to each of the containers will vary according to the different types of mixoplankton, as prey ingestion rates of some species are high, while other species eat very little or only feed when nutrients are limited (see under specific recommendations). It is important to maintain the correct balance of prey:mixoplankton cells as otherwise there is a risk that the culture will be taken over by the prey species, or conversely that the mixoplankton starve. If the mixotrophic capabilities of the cell being isolated is unknown, then the following principles could be used to decide on what prey type should be introduced to the containers.

Fig. 9. Multidishes are useful for isolation and initial growth of mixoplankton. To avoid evaporation, it is advisable to cover the wells with Parafilm below the lid.

- It can be assumed that, in essence, nanoplankton sized species ($< 15 \mu\text{m}$ ESD) are mainly bacterivorous mixoplankton. The cultures will contain bacteria; it is important to grow these species non-axenically in order to maintain the strain of the species as close to the natural isolated strains.
- The dinoflagellates are the exceptions to this rule. They are raptorial feeders and they prey generally most efficiently on prey items of their own size (Hansen & Calado 1998).
- Larger mixoplankton ($>15 \mu\text{m}$ ESD) generally do not exploit bacteria to any significant extent, so in these cases it is recommended to add protist prey of an appropriate size and species as early as possible.

As noted above, it is important to monitor the development of the cultures closely. This is to avoid the prey species from taking over the cultures by outgrowing the mixoplankton; especially if the tolerance of the mixoplankton to elevated pH is lower than that of the added prey (Section 4.2.3). Also, one should bear in mind that there are instances where the mixoplankton species feed very little or only when nutrients are limiting. It is therefore important to keep the initial level of nutrients in the medium quite low (say equivalent to f/20 or lower). This may be done by centrifuging the prey culture stock and re-suspend it in FSW before administering it to the mixoplankton. In this way the inoculum added contains negligible amounts of nutrients from the prey stock.

The containers should initially be checked daily using a compound, inverted or dissecting microscope depending upon the size of cells isolated (Section 4.2.1). The cultures will contain bacteria (as most cultures will be non-axenic). There is always a risk of contamination with other eukaryotic cells, which should be avoided through using standard aseptic techniques. In case of contamination with other protists the entire process has to be repeated. Therefore, it is important to be particularly careful with keeping the stock cultures of the newly isolated mixoplankton contaminant free by employing aseptic techniques during

the checking process. In some instances, the mixoplankton cannot keep up with the growth of the prey. This will be evident during the daily checks and it is important that the mixoplankton cells are transferred to new containers with fresh medium using a micropipette to prevent the prey species from dominating the culture.

It is unlikely that all the isolated cells will grow; generally, only a fraction of the isolated cells will survive and grow. Selection of mixoplankton cells for culture should be of the strains (coming from one cell) that grow well, and are from cultures that are not contaminated with other protists (excepting the prey). If there is a need to change the temperature or salinity for the culture, then this should be undertaken carefully, stepwise, over a few days. Any such alterations will be species-specific and needs to be established through trail-error experimentation.

Establishing cultures of specific species may be difficult for many different reasons. It may be necessary to undertake the steps described in Section 5.1.1 several times before successfully establishing a culture. In some cases, single cell isolation can prove difficult, and in such cases, one could consider isolation of several cells into each of the initial containers. Success rates are often substantially higher with this technique.

When good growth has been obtained in some containers, single cells are selected for preparation of clonal cultures. If one is not searching for a particular species, it will often be beneficial to add prey directly to the natural sea water sample with all its organisms and see which species will grow successfully; thereafter, isolate species that could be of interest for the particular research questions.

5.1.2 Identification

When cultures have been established, the next step will be to identify the species. This is best done using a combination of molecular and microscopic techniques. Microscopic techniques can be biased because haploid and diploid stages may occur, which may look quite different. This is well known for haptophytes (e.g., Larsen & Edvardsen 1998) and cryptophytes (Hoff and Bell 2020, Altenburger et al. 2020). Molecular methods may not be appropriate if the reference sequences deposited in the database are not associated with morphological descriptions. This problem is recognised for choreotrich and oligotrich ciliates (Santoferra et al. 2017). Specific guidance and help should be sought for identification as this is a complex exercise requiring expert intervention.

5.1.3 Mixoplankton culture upscaling for experimentation with upper trophic levels

In comparison with the volumes required for ecophysiological research at the mixoplankton level, the use of mixoplankton for experimentation as prey for upper trophic levels (i.e. copepods) poses the need for culture upscaling to larger volumes and larger quantities.

In the case of copepods, a major component of zooplankton, and given their size and feeding rates, replicated bottles of 500-2000 mL volume and cell suspensions with concentrations up to several thousand cells mL⁻¹ will be required in experiments. Given also the time scales of copepod physiology and growth, incubations may require several days to allow copepod to condition to the mixoplankton prey, with frequent refreshment of the mixoplankton suspensions to ensure nutritional conditions. In addition, once adulthood is reached,

copepods usually are used for experimentation within a relatively narrow timeframe for effective feeding and egg production estimates before aging takes over. In practice, careful planning and sequential inoculation of large volume cultures with the targeted mixoplankton are required to be able to satisfy the copepod conditioning demands.

Culturing of mixoplankton in large volumes (5-20 L) implies the use of containers (e.g., Pyrex bottles, polycarbonate Nalgene carboys) which will have a different surface to volume ratio of the culture when compared to rounded bottom flasks. In the light of this, the bottom layer, where many settling mixoplankton tend to accumulate, will have a limited contact with the surface. Hence, to ensure a correct gas exchange, it is always good practice to only fill the container up to the half and provide a gentle manual mixing and/or bubbling for resuspension and aeration.

Additionally, as mixoplankton consume their own prey, and if at the same time the mixoplankton prey can be also consumed by the copepod, confusing results will be the outcome since the top predator (copepod) will be feeding on both the mixoplankton and the mixoplankton prey. In these cases, careful daily monitoring of the mixoplankton culture, spiked with small amounts of prey, can allow to obtain high concentrations of mixoplankton with very few remaining prey at the time of experimentation with copepods.

Similarly, when performing elemental and stoichiometric analyses of the mixoplankton species (as prey for copepods), the presence of ungrazed prey into the mixoplankton culture would bias the real contribution of mixoplankton to the C, N and P content. Therefore, it is recommended that mixoplankton are provided with necessary food for growth but at levels that can be easily controlled and quickly grazed down. In practice, only mixoplankton species that are kept well in the laboratory and attain high growth rates will prove suitable.

5.2 Specific recommendations for different mixoplankton functional groups

This section provides specific guidance on how to isolate and establish cultures of the following mixoplankton functional groups:

- (1) CM: constitutive mixoplankton which fall within two different allometric groupings:
 - a. nano-CM: nanoplankton within the size range of 2-20 μm ESD, which are CMs
 - b. micro-CM: microplankton within the size range of 20-200 μm ESD, which are CMs
- (2) GNCM: generalist non-constitutive mixoplankton
- (3) pSNCM: plastidic specialist non-constitutive mixoplankton

5.2.1 Constitutive mixoplankton (CM)

The initial isolation of a CM species can in principle be done without adding prey, but recent studies have indicated that CMs may lose their ability to feed if kept without prey for years (Blossom et al. 2020). Thus, care should be taken if/when using species that have been kept for many years in culture collections for studies on mixotrophy in CMs. Prior to acquiring cultures, information should be sought from the culture collections about the conditions of maintenance of the CM mixoplankton species – specifically asking whether the cultures have been maintained in axenic or non-axenic conditions.

Types of prey for nano-CMs include bacteria and small protists, typically less than $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$ ESD, while the prey for micro-CMs differ among the species. Some species are quite prey selective and will only feed on a few prey species (e.g., *Fragilidium* spp, Skovgaard 1996), while others are quite omnivorous (e.g., *Karlodinium* spp, Berge et al. 2012, Jeong et al. 2010). Consequently, if information about prey type and size (and ideally nutrient conditions) is not available for the isolated species, this needs to be addressed at the time of (concurrently with) isolation.

Fig. 10. Sequence of four photos showing the ingestion of the cryptophyte, *Rhodomonas salina*, by the CM dinoflagellate *Karlodinium armiger*. From top left to bottom right: after 0, 20, 50 and 80 sec.

Almost all CMs require light for growth. A few species/strains can grow in darkness if fresh prey are supplied, although this is at a decreased growth rate; e.g., the dinoflagellates *Fragilidium* spp (Skovgaard 1996) and *Karlodinium veneficum* (Calbet et al. 2011).

5.2.2 Non-constitutive mixoplankton (NCM)

Very few **NCM** species are available from protist culture collections, so strains will need to be isolated prior to experiments. NCMs can be split into generalist NCMs (GNCMs) and specialist NCMs (SNCMs) (Mitra et al. 2016, Flynn et al. 2019; section 3).

NCMs include many dinoflagellates and ciliates, as well as amoebic groups, like foraminiferans and radiolarians. Successful cultures of NCM dinoflagellates and ciliates have been established, while NCM foraminiferans and radiolarians have not yet been brought into culture (perhaps because they rely on water movement and thus require culturing in larger bottles held on a plankton wheel).

NCMs are strongly dependent upon the addition of prey at the time of isolation. However, the species then differ considerably with regard to prey specificity and ingestion rates. Below, we provide some guidelines for the culture of the different types of NCMs.

GNCMs are commonly found among the ciliates; this functional type has yet to be discovered in dinoflagellates. GNCM ciliates have been grown on small protists in the size range 2-12 μm ESD (Gifford 1985, McManus et al. 2018, Maselli et al. 2020). They generally seem to be omnivorous and may successfully be grown on many different protist groups, including green algae, haptophytes, cryptophytes, diatoms, and dinoflagellates (Jonsson 1986; Stoecker et al. 1988 a and b, Maselli et al. 2020). However, in a species like *Strombidium rassoulzadegani*, the ability to grow in the dark has been shown to be dependent upon prey type. When fed a cryptophyte and a green alga this species could not grow in the dark. However, if it was fed a dinoflagellate as prey, the ciliate can grow well in darkness (McManus et al. 2012). GNCM ciliates can be difficult to get into culture when feeding them on monocultures of prey. Thus, it is recommended in the initial phases of isolation to feed GNCM species a mixture of prey or change the prey species if the GNCM does not maintain its growth rate.

SNCMs can further be split into eSNCMs, rSNCMs and pSNCMs.

a) eSNCMs are protists that harbour intact endo- or ecto-symbionts, and can be found among ciliates (Stoecker et al. 2009), dinoflagellates (Hansen and Tillmann 2020), and Rhizaria (Not et al. 2016, Leles et al. 2017). These protists usually contain just one endo/ectosymbiotic species, but some species with ectosymbionts have been observed with several symbionts (e.g., Tarangkoon et al. 2010). Some strains of the eSNCM green *Noctiluca scintillans* have been shown to survive in culture without applying prey (Furuya et al. 2006, Saito et al. 2006), while other strains of the same species have been reported to lose their endosymbionts; the latter strains can grow without the symbionts, if fed prey regularly (Hansen et al. 2004, Furuya et al. 2006, Saito et al. 2006).

The extent to which the eSNCMs have “permanent” symbionts is unknown in many cases. For some, the symbionts are free-living and are replenished through occasional feeding; e.g., various marine species within the foraminifera and rhizaria groups (Not et al. 2016), and the freshwater ciliate *Paramecium bursaria* (Kodama and Fujishima 2016). In other cases, e.g., the green *Noctiluca* and various Acantharia (Decelle et al. 2015, Brisbin et al. 2018), the endosymbionts appear to have adapted to a life inside the eSNCM. Indeed, for the dinoflagellate green *Noctiluca scintillans* the symbiont species has not been found free-living in natural waters yet. *Noctiluca* itself seems to be omnivorous (Zhang et al. 2016), although most data come from studies of the heterotrophic form of the species – the red *Noctiluca scintillans*.

Only two eSNCMs have been brought into culture - the marine green *Noctiluca scintillans*, and the freshwater *Paramecium bursaria*. While various attempts have been made to culture different rhizarian species, to date none of these attempts have been successful. So, bringing new species into culture will require a substantial amount of effort and a range of initial test experiments. The first step in isolating these kinds of species is to figure out if their symbionts are “permanent” or are supplied via ingestion. The next step is to search for prey that the species in question either can incorporate or provide nutrients to the host so that endo/ectosymbionts are retained and replicated.

b) rSNCMs can be found among both ciliates and dinoflagellates. They acquire phototrophic capabilities from specific prey items. They do not keep the ingested prey intact, but reduce it in various ways often retaining prey nuclei, prey mitochondria, and prey cytoplasm with intact prey ribosomes. Some of these species can be cultured in the dark (e.g., the dinoflagellates *Amphidinium poechiochrom* and *Gymnodinium gracilentum*), while other species require light for sustained growth (e.g., the dinoflagellates *Nusuttodinium aeruginosum* and *Amylax triacantha*; the ciliate red *Mesodinium* spp) (Skovgaard 2006, Jakobsen et al. 2007, Park et al. 2013, Kim et al. 2014, Drumm et al. 2017). rSNCMs often ingest only few prey cells per day and this needs to be considered when culturing them to avoid the prey overgrowing the mixoplankton.

rSNCMs generally seem to grow well only when fed cryptophytes, which they feed on directly, except for *Amylax triacantha* which retrieves the cryptophytes via other mixotrophs that contain the cryptophytes. The planktonic red *Mesodinium* spp (the *Mesodinium rubrum/major* species complex) ingest a range of cryptophytes, but they can only retain and grow on certain cryptophyte genera (within the *Teleaulax/Plagioselmis/Geminigera* clade (TPG clade), which supplies the host with chloroplasts and prey nuclei (see review by Hansen et al. 2013). The *Mesodinium* species associated with the benthos (*Mesodinium chamaeleon*, and *M. coatsi*) seem to have higher ingestion rates than the red planktonic *Mesodinium* spp, and to be less selective in their diets (Moestrup et al. 2012, Moeller and Johnson 2018, Kim and Park 2019). However, in the case of *M. coatsi*, it has been shown that this species grow well on *Chroomonas* and *Storeatula*, but not on *Teleaulax* spp, (Kim and Park 2019).

Prey selection has not been studied among the dinoflagellates. *G. gracilentum* (marine) has been grown on *Rhodomonas salina* (Skovgaard 1998, Jakobsen et al. 2000), while *Nusuttodinium poechiochrom* (marine) and *Nusuttodinium aeruginosum* (freshwater) have been grown on *Chroomonas* spp (Jakobsen et al. 2000, Drumm et al. 2017). Cultures of *Amylax triacantha* (dinoflagellate) have been established on *Mesodinium rubrum* only (Park et al. 2013, Kim et al. 2014). Such cultures require the logistic challenge of maintaining several species dependent upon each other.

c) pSNCMs

pSNCMs are true plastid specialist NCMs, and they have so far only been found in the dinoflagellate genus *Dinophysis*. Eight species have so far been cultured (Nagai et al. 2020), all on *M. rubrum* as the prey. *Dinophysis* ingests the bulk part of the *M. rubrum* cell using a peduncle (a drinking-straw-like structure). Upon entry into *Dinophysis*, the chloroplasts are quickly separated out, while the other components of the prey are digested. The other NCMs that sequester chloroplasts either also sequester other prey organelles, or sequester a broad range of prey chloroplasts and are thus either rSNCMs or NCMs, respectively (see above).

Dinophysis spp have considerable control of ingested chloroplasts, and it has been shown that *Dinophysis acuminata* and *D. acuta* can divide the sequestered chloroplasts, at least a couple of times in prey-starved cultures (Rusterholz et al. 2017). It has also been shown that prey-starved *D. acuta* produces photosynthetic and photoprotective

pigments (Hansen et al. 2016). *Dinophysis* spp require light for growth and cultures have so far only been established using the ciliate *M. rubrum* as prey (see review by Hansen et al. 2013). To grow *Dinophysis* spp, a small food chain needs to be set up in the laboratory, involving cultures of a *Teleaulax* sp. as well as a culture of *M. rubrum*. It is essential that the *M. rubrum* culture that is used as prey for *Dinophysis* is without any *Teleaulax* cells in, otherwise the cryptophyte will overgrow the *Dinophysis*. *Dinophysis* itself cannot ingest single *Teleaulax* cells.

6 Summary

This manual provides guidance in the sampling, isolation and culture of mixoplankton. The most important and critical steps are as follows:

- Purchase the right materials to be used for isolation (check adequacy of components, some mixoplankton are vulnerable to addition of anti-stick chemicals applied to plastic materials).
- Have the necessary culture facilities, where you can control light and temperature.
- Control the predator:prey ratio in your cultures. Avoid overgrowth of the prey due to photon flux density, nutrient concentrations, nutrient source and ratios, and prey:predator ratios.
- Avoid elevated pH during phototrophic growth by bubbling with atmospheric air or CO₂ and add extra inorganic carbon if necessary, for instance when lowering the salinity of the culture medium.
- Upscale to large volume with synchronisation/control of nutritional status of all the trophic levels involved.

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